

THE METHODOLOGY OF ORGANIZING EXPERIMENT STUDIES AIMED AT IMPROVING CULTURAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION UNIVERSITIES BASED ON AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH

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Abstract. This article is dedicated to experimenting with studies in English at diverse universities. There is shown the aims, tasks, and results of experiments as well as the impact of English on cultural competence in both teaching and studying. So, it is divided into three levels: critical, formative, and evaluation. All the processes of experimenting are given in mentioned levels. In experimenting, given project works such as “Debate”, “Start-up”, “Case-study” and modern methods Crocodile, Questionnaire, SWOT, Think wane, activities like play around, kick the ball, chain the story, dance on the aim, presentations to open students’ abilities. Moreover, the explanation of “General English” is pointed to the formation of English. If learners are good at general English, all other fields in English including business, engineering, and others will be more straightforward, in addition, it will be more efficient to deal with APTIS, IELTS, TESOL, and other international courses. So, in the experimenting part, there are given three universities, GPAs, grades, and lesson weeks according to the Korean educational syllabus. The number of students is 150 in the experimental group and 223 students in the control group.

Keywords: experimenting, cultural competence, credit-module system, Business English, pedagogical technologies, activities, methods, students.

МЕТОДОЛОГИЯ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ ЭКСПЕРИМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ ЗАНЯТИЙ НА СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ КУЛЬТУРНЫХ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЙ В ВУЗАХ НА ОСНОВЕ ИНТЕГРАТИВНОГО ПОДХОДА

Аннотация. Эта статья посвящена экспериментам с изучением английского языка в разных университетах. Показаны цели, задачи и результаты экспериментов, а также влияние английского языка на культурную компетентность как в преподавании, так и в обучении. Итак, она делится на три уровня: критический, формирующий и оценочный. Все процессы экспериментирования приведены в указанных уровнях. При экспериментировании с такими проектными работами, как «Дебаты», «Start up», «Case study» и современными методами «Crocodile», «Опросник», «SWOT», «Подумайте об упадке», такие действия, как игра, удар по мячу, цепочка историй, танец на цель, презентации для раскрытия способностей учащихся. Более того, объяснение «общего английского» указывает на формирование английского языка. Если учащиеся хорошо владеют общим английским языком, все остальные области английского языка, включая бизнес, инженерное дело и другие, будут более простыми, кроме того, будет более эффективно справляться с APTIS, IELTS, TESOL и другими международными курсами. Итак, в экспериментальной части даются три университета, средние баллы, оценки и учебные недели согласно корейской образовательной программе. Количество студентов в экспериментальной группе 150 участников, в контрольной группе 223 участника.

Ключевые слова: экспериментирование, культурологическая компетентность, кредитно-модульная система, деловой английский, педагогические технологии, деятельность, методика, студенты.

INTRODUCTION

It is obvious that education plays a main role in our society. Each field shows its peculiarity and aim. Everyone at the university faces different types of English. Sometimes some people are not interested in English, others are non-stop learning the English language. To attract students to learn English, different experiments are conducted in order to choose the best way of teaching. Experimenting studies in the research work can be a sample. From the year 2020/2021, the credit-module system was indicated step by step to the educational system of Uzbekistan universities and institutions. The aim of the credit-module system is to call learners to study individually and enhance self-studying, integration of cultural competence among the students and teachers, and others.

During the experience, we could observe and develop professional methodological defects and work on them as well as achieve the best results, and develop the factors of professional preparation in education and know how to use them. Besides, observing and enhancing cooperation among foreign specialists can show more beneficial ways, and local teachers and professors learn professional skills and methods from foreign professors in order to develop aspects of integration knowledge. Besides, we consider the following tasks which have positive attitudes on education. It is important to say at the beginning as well as at the end of the experience, there were used several activities, quizzes, questionnaires, and other authentic materials for developing the teaching of "Foreign languages". So all we can call "practical activities".

Currently, to achieve innovation in education, new pedagogical technologies and computer technologies are closely related. These factors were tested in groups during the lesson, and we were able to see the integration of intercultural competence. The teacher's method of delivering lessons through new methods was also shown. Special demonstrations (presentations) were prepared for each lesson and were used as a basis for the growth of the teacher's level and professional training.

It is worth saying that all mentioned above is more effective to make students interested in education through modern education. Traditional classes have their benefits. But digital education is giving us an increase in the intelligence of our students. In order to improve the process of integration of intercultural competence in education, we need to pay attention to the modern education of both students and teachers. If the teacher provides online training in the course of the lesson, regardless of the nationality of the student, the competence of the teacher and the students will increase their knowledge.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

For experience, it was selected three universities, one is Ajou University in Tashkent (a foreign university) and two local universities, Jizzakh and Andijan polytechnic universities. In addition, Ajou University in Tashkent (a branch of Korea University, ranked among the top 1000 in the world, ranked 531st). The faculties of Electrical and computer engineering were chosen for experience activities.

At the emphasis stage, the current state of professional training was studied, and educational as well as methodological support in High Educational Universities: sample programs, curriculum, working curriculum, textbooks, educational literature, and manuals were analyzed, as well as field-specific English lessons, were observed and studies were conducted in order to study professional components. The content of the program was determined, the

organizational and technological status of the professional training process was ensured, and questionnaires (for students) were.

In teaching a foreign language (English), first of all, taking focus on intercultural competence, it is important to teach the language in a field-related way with authentic materials. While teaching the language, for example, if we take industry-specific Business English, various activities, such as kahoot.com online tests and Business English “Role-plays”, and “start-up” project works, were conducted to properly deliver to students in the field. Business English roundtable discussions and practical exercises such as “Debate” were conducted, and undoubtedly, students were also able to develop skills such as correct speaking, grammatically correct writing, and listening comprehension. During the trial sphere, these activities were very effective, and modern technologies were very useful for teaching English.

We aimed to identify, study and analyze the problems faced by the field of English language teaching in our research. Firstly, we reviewed lesson plans through the syllabus of how to conduct textbooks related to the field in foreign countries (Republic of Korea), and through these programs, lesson plans and activities were created in combining local and foreign programs of Higher Educational Universities. It was implemented for tests to institutes and universities. Monitoring of the results in different ways (giving students a specific topic, watching and observing their independent preparation, and developing language skills) was carried out together. For example, one of the new methods of classes is to organize outdoor activities with students, to show them the English language related to the field through “role play”, to develop speaking and listening skills, to draw their ideas on the topic on posters, and as a result of free communication, the students aimed at giving freedom to speech and the goal was achieved. At the end of these free lessons, a positive conversation was held with the students and the goal was achieved.

As has been mentioned, we added a roundtable discussion called “Debate” to the students’ “project work”. In this, the students were divided into two groups, and the situations related to the field of Business English were given to the opposite side. One group had to show the positive side of the issue, and the second group had the negative side of the issue, proving this situation with examples. The groups had to get out of this situation by reasoning and speaking fluent English without fighting or crying at each other. A sample of methods can be a “Case-study” too. The Case-Study project work also taught students to plan business in advance. Since this was a first for the students, there was a bit of debate among the participants, raising their voices to show that they were right. In fact, the debate consists of the delivery of students’ ideas fluently, with examples of the basics. It consists in being able to control the ability to use restraint and hand movements in any situation. Regardless of the country, the English language, conversational tones, and solving business problems were done on the basis of certain steps. For this reason, business issues and problematic situations from different countries were presented in the discussion. Our goal is to explain and apply the generalization of intercultural competence in young students. Learning any branch of English, we should pay great attention to vocabulary. We must learn to analyze and speak grammatically correctly. Language teaching in any Higher Education Institution has types of speech activities and problems encountered in it. To eliminate them, teaching and learning are the most important tasks. During this time, the following practical exercises were carried out:

1. “Crocodile” method - pronouncing words correctly and explaining one’s thoughts;

2. “Questionnaire” forming and memorizing types of grammatical sentences;
3. SWOT (strengths, weaknesses, goals, and negative aspects and reaching a certain conclusion) Identifying the four sides of the issue.
4. Think wane - teaching students to think quickly.

Furthermore, different activities and methods were conducted in our experience. For example, “play around”, “kick the ball”, “dance on the aim”, “chain the story”, and “the truth” (getting the truth or the situation), creating presentations.

There are given 16 weeks for teaching students, and during four months all new methods and techniques were explained and conducted.

Week 1	Orientation + Unit 1. Jobs and Responsibilities
Week 2	Unit 2. Telephoning to make arrangements
Week 3	Unit 3. Organizations + DEBATE
Week 4	Unit 4. Planning Ahead
Week 5	Unit 5. Growth and Development
Week 6	Unit 6. Problem solving+ CASE STUDY
Week 7	Unit 7. Telephoning to exchange information
Week 8	Midterm exam
Week 9	Orientation + Unit 1. Jobs and Responsibilities
Week 10	Unit 8. Visitors
Week 11	Unit 9. Reporting on progress
Week 12	Unit 10. Describing trends + ROLE PLAY
Week 13	Unit 11. Products and Services
Week 14	Unit 12. Comparing Options
Week 15	Unit 13. Meeting
Week 16	Unit 14. Presentations + START UP (project)

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

In the period of language teaching, it is reasonable to give freedom to learners, for example, to demonstrate the parts of the lesson how they want (grammar, listening comprehension, reading, various interesting activities). This is the main purpose of the credit module system. Giving students more opportunities to learn science is a remarkable sign. Then “knowledgeable competition” is formed among students in the field of education. This, in turn, is growth in the field of science of our country.

It is important to analyze and monitor the effectiveness of the mathematical and statistical analysis of the results obtained from the experimental work and the ability of teachers to organize integrated lessons and demonstration activities in cooperation with teachers of different cultures.

Paying attention to the acquisition of foreign language (English) and specialized English (Business English, Engineering English) together with intercultural competence in the 1st and 2nd year of students. Experimental work was carried out in the designated experimental areas. On the basis of the integration of cultural competence, scientific work (dissertations) on the

development of teaching training of teachers and its further improvement were organized in three stages. Tests, formative and evaluation pilot-test works were organized.

In the first emphasis stage (2019-2020), the methodological and theoretical foundations of the research were studied, the scientific literature of higher education institutions, manuals, and scientific works of foreign scientists was reviewed, the main scientific directions (object, topic, goal, tasks, research, and research) and language researches were conducted for theoretical and practical approaches to the problems encountered while teaching. In addition, the dissertation works of Akhmedova Nodira Mukhtorjonovna, and Riskulova Kamola Djuraevna were studied, as well as the book “Cooperative Pedagogy” by Abdullaeva Sh., Choriev Sh., scientific literature of B.S. Gershunsky was carefully studied.

The research involved the identification, study, and analysis of the problems faced in teaching a language or a language in a field. We studied the similarities and differences between the foreign university and local universities, the preparation of the teachers of different nationalities, and the teaching methods and methods used by their work experience, and as a result of the analysis, we learned something new. That is, we were able to give students an opportunity to work more on their own, and by comparing the level of knowledge of students from other countries in a positive way, and showing any topic or task according to their imagination. Because the teacher does not only teach and check the tasks but always shows positive growth in the student’s language learning. Foreign teachers assign 80% of tasks to students, and the remaining 20% consists only of partial explanation, guidance, and evaluation of tasks. That is why self-studying in foreign educational institutions is given higher marks than in local educational institutions. Also, on the basis of self-study or tasks, students are evaluated by hearing positive and negative criticisms from their group mates and the teacher sums up these criticisms and gives a whole opinion (feedback), and with this process, cultural competence is developed between the student and the teacher in relation to science or the field (related to language).

The results of the emphasis phase of the experiment-test are based on an integrative approach, including cultural competence, by analyzing the psychological-pedagogical literature and learning the experiences of foreign professors, bringing them to local students, and vice versa, learning from foreign professors, creating new teaching methods and techniques, and passing them on to foreign students. Both the application and the goal help define the task.

The second formative stage of our research (2020-2021) mainly focused on pedagogy. The organization of theoretical and practical foundations of intercultural competence is devoted to the creation and justification of an integrative process. In order to know the status of the research work, in fact, the teacher's own experience, knowledge, giving encouragement (motivation) to the student who is not interested in education, giving education beyond knowledge in the teacher, that is, an individual psychological approach to each student, the culture of treatment, the communication styles of the student or teacher of different nationalities, activities, even methods of preparing lesson plans were studied. There are a lot of online classes, tests, and quizzes, especially nowadays in education. An example is kahoot.com. From this site, students are given 10-minute tests on the topics covered. The tests will be conducted with all students in the group, and three (3) winning students will be determined by giving the correct answer. The most interesting thing is that such digital lessons teach students to be thorough, intelligent, and resourceful, and teachers to strive for innovation. In the

formative level of the experiment, the above-mentioned types of training improved the content and essence of intercultural lessons and presentations. Modern educational technologies, interactive practical exercises, and interesting project works (project works) were implemented in our experimental work. The speaking part, which is always a problem in English, was a problem. To develop this skill, all the available activities, video, listening, and speaking skills have been removed and the existing gap has been filled. It was seen that our activities should help students to think freely, think more deeply, and use materials more in language acquisition.

During the evaluation stage of our study, we used evaluation criteria such as special guidelines or European standards such as **A/A+**, **B/B+**, **C/C+**, **D/D+** and **F**.

A+ / A - excellent (depending on grade and participation + points are given)

B+ / B – good (depending on grade and participation + points are given)

C+ / C- Satisfactory (+ points awarded based on grade and attendance)

D+ / D- is the lowest score

F- indicates failure, i.e. failure to pass a course or assignment.

Also, students were assessed through guidelines for special assignments, such as project work. This evaluation system was also offered to High Educational Institutions. Of course, the credit module system includes just such an assessment. As it has been said, in the credit module system, the greatest attention is focused on the student's search and hard work on himself. Scores were awarded to students through the criteria. The total course is 100 points, if the student scores 95-100 points, then the overall indicator is A+. Then, during the course, 10 points will be awarded for four projects (total of 40 points), 25 points for intermediate and final works (total of 50 points), and the remaining 10 points will be awarded for class participation and homework.

GRADE	SCORE	GPA (grade point average)
A+	95-100	4.5
A0	90-94	4.0
B+	85-89	3.5
B0	80-84	3.0
C+	75-79	2.5
C0	70-74	2.0
D+	65-69	1.5
D0	60-64	1.0
F	0-59	0

A total of 373 students were involved in the experimental work.

Places for experimenting	Participants	First course	Second course
Ajou University in Tashkent	125	50	75
Andijan Machine Building Institute	123	50	73
Jizzah Polytechnic Institute	125	50	75
Total	373	150	223

CONCLUSION

Questionnaires (surveys) were conducted in foreign and local higher education institutions on the basis of the integration of different nationalities, that is, intercultural competence, and for the purpose of a true assessment of this situation. A total of 373 students from the 1st and 2nd stages participated.

All four steps required due diligence. This is because the four skills are interrelated. Of course, when pronouncing words and sentences, errors in pronunciation and lack of accents in words were noticed. But after a few sessions, this situation will change in a positive direction. The reason for his inability to act as he is presented in the role is his inability to fully express himself as the character of the subject in the authentic material, his lack of body language, and his lack of tone. Also, great attention was paid to the participants' speaking, role-playing, behavior, and listening comprehension. Of course, in some places, there were cases where **student A** did not respond to the questions of **student B**, but the student continued to express himself without losing himself in the role. There was able to show appropriate hand movements. After the experience, explaining the content of the question to the students, listening to more authentic conversations on the topic so that they can quickly learn the content of the topic while listening to each other, and why, presenting the exercises consistently and with a sense of responsibility, develops all the skills of the student and improves the characteristic of having international competence. Experiments have shown that non-traditional classes benefit more students than traditional classes. It was found through trial and error that the students should read a lot about the subject.

All classes from “General English”, courses such as IELTS, APTIS, and TESOL also come from the other sides. It is these three international certificates that have attracted the interest not only of Uzbekistan but also of all countries.

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